

Effect of Flexible Project Management Practices on Work-Life Balance Among Construction Engineers in Tamil Nadu

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Abstract: This study analyses the association between the work-life balance of construction workers and their productivity within a construction sector. A survey strategy was employed, administering 200 questionnaires to small and medium construction enterprises, resulting in 150 responses. Canonical correlation analysis was conducted to determine the connection between the predictor variable and the criterion latent variable set. A correlation exists between the work-life balance of construction workers and productivity in the construction sector. This effort aims to stimulate broader academic discourse and reinvigorate the necessity for revisiting work-life balance policies that will boost productivity. Construction organizations must formulate and execute work-life balance policies for construction workers at their workplaces.

Keywords: Work-life balance, Construction workers, productivity, policies, organizations.

Introduction

Work-life balance seeks to attain equilibrium between the stress experienced by individuals, their families, and their professional responsibilities. It is a synthesis of work and life whereby neither disrupts the other. Organizations in the construction industry are intricate and frequently undergo structural changes due to regional mobility and sectoral economic instability. This is likely attributable to traits such as male employees' capacity to endure both occupational and familial stressors, in addition to societal demands, among other factors. Consequently, construction businesses must implement work-life balance policies to enhance employee productivity. Formulating and executing work-life balance regulations will also mitigate health risks for individual workers. Previous research indicates that those who utilize their vacations and yearly leave exhibit much higher productivity compared to those who forgo such time off. Furthermore, employees' inability to disengage from work results in symptoms like burnout, adversely affecting their well-being.

Work-life balance policies inevitably enhance individual health, promote healthy choices, and enable both body and mind to function properly, hence increasing productivity. According to Bird[10], work-life balance enhances productivity by instructing individuals on how to allocate an equal amount of hours daily for professional and personal pursuits. Studies have also associated job schedule demands with the family functioning of construction

professionals in various jurisdictions. A survey of Australian civil engineers indicated that hours worked per week had a negative correlation with marriage satisfaction and a positive correlation with marital conflict. Mordi et al. [12] assert that work-life balance motivates people towards personal and organizational fulfilment, hence enhancing productivity [13].

Work-life balance in the construction sector:

McCann [17] posits that the temporal conflict in these two dimensions engenders a bidirectional imbalance. Consequently, work-life interference often prevails over family life. Work and home activities frequently collide, complicating the establishment of a border between the two. The construction worker and their company must identify adaptable ways to enhance productivity without compromising employee welfare, safety, and personal life. These adaptable solutions may manifest as work-life balance rules or programs designed to harmonize individuals' professional and familial responsibilities while simultaneously enhancing productivity.

Construction businesses can use any of the aforementioned work-life balance rules to mitigate work-life conflict and foster organizational commitment, ultimately leading to enhanced productivity. The construction company will benefit from WLB by enhancing commitment and teamwork, while individual employees will experience increased value, improved work-life balance, and reduced stress. Stevens et al. [26] conclude that work-life balance initiatives or policies exert varying effects on employees. Conversely, work-life balance rules enhance employee job satisfaction and health while simultaneously benefiting companies through reduced absenteeism and attrition, as well as heightened motivation, productivity, and performance. Construction firms can adopt diverse work-life balance policy measures that aid employees in effectively managing their job and familial obligations, enhance their well-being, and yield organizational advantages.

The evaluation is based on the effectiveness and efficiency of labor use during the construction process, as well as the suitability of labor allocation for particular activities at specified times and locations. Human-related factors include employee motivation, skill enhancement, communication, organizational culture, leadership, loyalty, commitment, and personal characteristics, whereas management-related factors involve the quality of supervision, resource management, site planning, constructability, and change management, among others.

Previous research has associated job schedule demands with the family functioning of construction professionals. For example, permitting construction workers to have flexible working hours, as noted by Kotey and Sharma[31], would enable them to establish their own start and end timings for the workday. WLB policies will consequently provide employees with sufficient time to address urgent family obligations. Furthermore, transportation given for employees to mitigate tardiness will ultimately result in increased production. It will ensure the safety of workers and foster a sense of recognition.

Moreover, providing annual vacation to construction workers will alleviate work-related stress and foster a balance between professional responsibilities and personal pursuits. The WLB technique proposed by Christopher[32] will enable individuals to engage in

responsibilities outside their professional obligations, fostering equilibrium among their work, personal, and familial activities.

Part-time arrangements serve as a strategy enabling construction workers with health issues, disabilities, or constrained availability, such as students in internships, to engage in the construction labor market, thereby enhancing their skills and acquiring work experience. Implementing a complimentary bus service for employees' children to commute to and from school may serve as an additional technique to enhance efficiency within the construction business. While many construction organizations may perceive such an approach as financially burdensome, it will mitigate tardiness, promote mental well-being among workers, and enhance productivity.

Implementing telework or telecommuting in the construction sector poses significant challenges; nonetheless, it is feasible for administrative and office personnel. It entails performing a portion of their routine tasks remotely rather than commuting to the office. Nonetheless, the majority of construction operations occur on-site. Telecommuting will enhance employees' pay and boost productivity in the construction sector.

Research Methodology:

The research employs a quantitative methodology utilizing survey questionnaires. Questionnaires were predominantly utilized as a data collecting instrument due to their capacity to efficiently gather extensive data from a substantial population. The questions needed to be articulated in a manner that was understandable to the subjects. Experts conducted testing, leading to essential revisions. Purposive, convenience, and snowball sampling strategies were employed, utilizing managing directors, senior project managers, and construction workers from government construction companies and consulting businesses to access the unit under investigation. Two hundred (200) questionnaires were submitted to various construction agencies and consulting businesses, of which 150 were returned, representing 87% response rate. Of the 150 questionnaires received, 30 were deemed invalid due to inaccuracies, among other issues. A total of 94% (n = 112) of the responders were male, while 6% (n = 8) were female. The ages of the responders varied from 20 to over 50 years. All participants were employed in construction firms classified as two different contractors.

A reliability analysis was conducted to see if the selected scale accurately represents the constructs being restrained. It is a facet in which two explanations being examined, which are equivalent concerning the construct being assessed, also yield equivalent outcomes. The Cronbach's alpha test was employed to evaluate the reliability of the poll. A recommended value, indicative of a high level of internal consistency, is suggested [36].

Table.1 Work-life balance strategies and productivity for variables

	Variables	Item Code Mean			Cronbach's
		Std Deviation			
		Productivity Variables			
1	Staff Motivation	SM	2.40	0.803	

2	Commitment	CT	2.60	0.803	0.939
3	Loyalty	LT	3.80	1.171	
4	Skills Development	SD	3.20	1.840	
5	Leadership	LS	3.40	1.024	
6	Organizational Culture	OC	3.00	1.420	
7	Communication	CM	3.60	1.024	
		WLB Predictor Variables			
1	Telework	TL	1.60	0.803	
2	Telework Part-Time	TL	1.60	0.803	0.882
3	Work telecommuting	PW	1.80	1.171	
4	Flexible Job Schedule	TC FS	1.60 4.00	0.803 0.889	
5	Transport for Workers	TW	2.80	1.332	
6	Flexible Working Hours	FH	4.00	0.635	
7	Leaves and Vacations	LV	2.80	1.476	
8	School bus for wards	SW	2.40	0.803	

Table 2 Reliability statistics - WLB factors

WLB Policies	Code	Productivity
Part-Time Work	PW	Staff Motivation
Flexible Working Hours	FH	Skill Development
Leaves and Vacations	LA	Communication
Flexible Job Schedule	FS	Organizational Setup
School bus for wards	SW	Leadership
Transport for Workers	TW	Loyalty
Telework	TL	Commitment
telecommuting	TC	

Canonical correlation:

Canonical correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between the predictor variable and the set of criterion latent variables. The primary objective was to

ascertain the quantity of canonical functions to be incorporated for analysis. The study produced four canonical functions because CCA often generates numerous functions associated with the variables in the diminished dependent variable set. Although all four tests in Table 3 yielded statistically significant results at the 0.05 level, the study employed the most prevalent test, Wilks' lambda (λ).

Wilks' lambda generally has the broadest applicability.

Table 3. Multivariate test of significance

Test Name	Value	Approx F	Hypoth DE	Error DF	Sig. of F
Pillai	0.2355	2.2978	16.00	589.00	0.002
Hotelling's	0.2831	2.5223	16.00	570.00	0.001
Wilks	0.7729	2.4226	16.00	430.70	0.002
Roy's	0.2731				

Source: Field study, 2022

Effect of Relationship:

It is vital to recognize that statistically important results can be significantly influenced by sample size, whereby minor, inconsequential effects may become statistically significant with sufficiently high sample sizes. The effect size in Canonical Correlation Analysis can be assessed using Wilks' lambda, which signifies an inverse effect size, or the proportion of variance not shared between the variable sets. Consequently, removing this value from 1 yields the total effect size, representing the variance shared by the variable sets for the complete model). The results collectively demonstrate that the model is statistically important and exhibits a moderate effect size.

Table 4 Eigen values and canonical correlations

Root No	Eigenvalue	Pct	Cum.Pct	Canon.Cor.	Sq. Cor
1	0.241	84.78	84.78	0.40	0.195
2	0.037	13.05	97.83	0.18	0.035
3	0.005	1.75	99.58	0.06	0.004
4	0.012	0.45	100.03	0.33	0.001

Source: Field study, 2022

Consequently, they would not be preserved for analysis. The research concludes that a significant canonical relationship exists between the two sets of latent variables.

Table 5 Dimension reduction analysis

Root Nr	Wilks L	F	Hypoth.DF	Error DF	Sig. of F
1 to 4	0.726	2.435	16.00	431.70	0.003

2 to 4	0.986	0.697	9.00	343.05	0.757
3 to 4	0.849	0.224	4.00	290.00	0.295
4 to 4	0.988	0.174	1.00	147.00	0.756

Source: Field study, 2022

Discussion

The study indicated that the majority of respondents recognize the significance and advantages of work-life balance policies inside their organizations. Work from home allows employees to meet familial or personal responsibilities and manage home emergencies. It will enable employees to manage both expected and unexpected circumstances pertaining to their familial and professional lives. An employee afforded the possibility of a flexible work schedule will be satisfied and motivated to earn similar opportunities in the future.

These skill sets will contribute to the long-term improvement of construction organizations. A flexible job schedule can promote job rotation among employees, thereby facilitating information transfer. It can be contended that offering transportation benefits to employees confers a competitive advantage over rivals. A construction firm gains advantages by attracting and maintaining its personnel, reducing payroll taxes, extending working hours, and establishing a reputation as an environmentally and employee-friendly entity..

Leaves may consist of study leave, sick leave, annual leave, or caregiving leave. It enables these people to acquire additional information, which is reinvested into the organizations to enhance production. Assessing health and safety requirements enables employees to enhance their physical capacity and boost productivity in the energy-intensive construction sector. Annual leave refers to the compensated time off granted to employees for recreational purposes, which they become eligible for after completing a specified duration of qualifying service with a particular firm.

The findings confirm that part-time work policies in the construction sector can aid individuals with career interruptions, homemakers, and promote a gradual transition for personnel nearing retirement. The part-time work strategy can optimize human resource utilization and enhance operational flexibility by offering supplementary covering during peak periods. Nevertheless, it will avert an employee from experiencing a fragmented focus while on site regarding when and whoever to collect their child. Consequently, it will alleviate stress and occasionally tardiness at the site.

This study acknowledges that flexible working hours, including part-time work, adaptable job schedules, transportation for employees' children to school, and transport for workers, are viable work-life balance policies that construction organizations in Tamilnadu can adopt. These factors frequently result in enhanced productivity within the construction sector.

Conclusion

WLC policies positively influence industry performance. Implementing WLC policies in diverse firms will enhance efficiency inside the organization. The lack of WLC rules in

construction organizations might result in low employee retention. Construction firms that acknowledge individuality and prioritize employee work-life balance policies and initiatives are likely to mitigate family-work fight, hence enhancing productivity within these businesses. Effective communication and comprehension of the broader implications of work-life balance regulations on construction productivity must be key to stakeholders and policymakers in the construction sector of emerging nations. The limited sample size may be considered a constraint. The lack of further demographic data regarding the ownership structure of construction organizations may also be seen as a limitation.

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